

INVESTMENT ACTIVITY AND INTRODUCTION OF ENTITIES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract. It is no exaggeration to say that investment constitutes a separate large department in the service sector of banks. This article describes in detail about Investment activity and introduction of entities in the service sector.

Keywords: service, investment, banking services, the image of the country, financial development, etc.

On the effective management of investment projects, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "If we can carefully formulate investment projects for regions and sectors for investors who want to invest in our economy, we can achieve a positive result in this matter". In fact, the President emphasized that the most important task of the government should be the unconditional implementation of projects involving direct foreign investment, providing all-round assistance to foreign investors. Putting an end to the practice of delaying the utilization of the main part of investments to the last months of the year, it was noted that in all sectors and regions it is necessary to reach at least 35% in the first half of the year and 70% in the first nine months. In particular, the features of the organization of investment activities in the regions of our country, the organization of activities of regional venture funds in the financing of investment projects, the improvement of mechanisms for the allocation of syndicated loans in the financing of investment projects, and the improvement of the efficiency of the use of internal resources, including population savings, in the organization of investment activities must Improving the method of syndicated lending of large investment projects by commercial banks requires strengthening the long-term resource base of banks.

For this purpose, it is necessary to reduce the mandatory reserve rates set by the Central Bank for long-term deposits of commercial banks, and to place state-owned funds as long-term deposits in commercial banks that provide syndicated lending in the main sectors of the economy, and to attract funds by securitizing loans to high-performance projects. increases the possibilities of financing investment projects and the market for other objects (for example, precious metals and products, etc.).

Investments are long-term capital investments in various sectors of the economy, infrastructure, social programs, environmental protection both domestically and abroad. In modern market economies, a significant part of investment is financial. Investments play an important role both at the macro level and at the micro level. They determine the future of the country as a whole, an individual business entity and are the driving force in the development of the economy. In recent years, there has been a trend towards a reduction in real investment, which has had a negative impact on the acceleration of scientific and technological progress (STP) and the development of the entire national economic complex.

The investment crisis in the country turned out to be deeper than the general economic one, although both of them are closely interconnected and interdependent. Investment activity as an investment and the implementation of practical actions in order to make a profit or achieve another beneficial effect is associated with the formation of an investment portfolio. In general, the investment portfolio of any organization includes not only a portfolio of investments in securities, but also a portfolio of real investments and a portfolio of investments in the working capital of the organization. Investment activity in market conditions of management is carried out in the investment market, which consists of the market of real investment objects, the market of financial investment objects and the market of innovative investment objects. The market for real investment objects includes the market for direct capital investments, the real estate market and the market for other objects (for example, precious metals and products, etc.).

In particular, thanks to preferential loans allocated to the service sector within the framework of entrepreneurship development programs, additional loans allocated to the sector by commercial banks from their own funds, and other benefits, many of our young men and women are self-employed in the service sector, to a source of income. We have seen and witnessed the results of regions, cities and districts that effectively used these opportunities. It should be said that in this area, based on the specificity of each region, it is also extremely important to create a new methodology for expanding services, introducing new types of services, and introducing best practices and model projects. In this process, a project-analytical center for the development of services was established at the National Bank of Uzbekistan, and its branches were opened in all regions. Now they provide sample ready-made business projects to residents and provide comprehensive services from vocational training to starting a business. The head of our state is creating all the conditions and providing the necessary funds before giving assignments to the officials in any direction. If local governments use these funds honestly and implement projects on time, thousands of new jobs will be created.

In the words of the President, "every minister is a patriot, pulls his own cart, appreciates the money given to him and delivers it to his place, people will believe him." Therefore, from now on, officials should act in their direction for the development of services, and the head of each ministry and department should completely change their attitude and approach to providing services to the population in the area of their responsibility. While promoting important initiatives in this regard, the head of state stated that there is an opportunity to increase the volume of communication and internet services by at least 2 times and programming by 3 times due to the further expansion of the participation of the private sector in the information sector, lowering the prices and increasing the quality. In the same way, the directions necessary to be used in the system of all ministries and agencies were shown. In order to bring services closer to the population, the importance of building service centers from light constructions in neighborhoods was emphasized, and it was decided to establish special streets for trade and services in 28 cities and district centers with a population of more than 150,000. They can accommodate 100,000 business entities. Service provision is a sector with great potential for providing employment and creating new jobs.

The real growth of local income can be clearly seen, first of all, from the development of services. In this regard, we focus on the development of the service sector and strengthening its role in the structure of the economy. This sector can not only provide jobs, especially in

rural areas, but also increase the income of the population. The service industry is the most profitable industry in the world today. In our country, special attention is being paid to the further development of this direction, to all-round support of entrepreneurs operating in the service sector. Especially in the following years, financial institutions play an important role in providing loans to entrepreneurs who want to start entrepreneurship in this direction.

In such a situation, the type of concession security can be a bank guarantee, and to secure the credit obligations of the concessionaire itself, a guarantee of state authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation or municipal authorities is used. For these purposes, it is proposed to use the so-called guarantee of payments "on termination of obligations". Its essence lies in the fact that in the event of the termination of the concession agreement, regardless of the reasons for this event, the concessor reimburses the creditor banks for the entire amount of loans received under the concession. In this case, the risks and liability under the concession agreement will be borne by the grantor and the concessionaire, and not by the bank.

In order to actively involve financial and credit organizations of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation in investment processes in the housing and communal sector, it is necessary to improve the legal framework for investment processes, address the issues of reducing and redistributing investors' risks, debug the collateral accounting system, ensure the interaction of government bodies, banking and business structures in the investment, information, organizational mediation, to develop an insurance system and a guarantee market, as well as an institutional investment infrastructure by creating the interest of consulting, marketing agencies, and engineering firms. In particular, the development of a regulatory framework for regulating concessions of utility infrastructure facilities, attracting credit resources, including in the form of external loans, can increase the investment attractiveness of the housing and communal complex. The development of the insurance system involves voluntary housing insurance by citizens. It is assumed that persons who have not insured housing, instead of housing destroyed by fire, flood, and other natural disasters, will be provided with housing on a social rental basis temporarily, without ownership rights. Citizens who have insured housing will be able to count on an apartment in a house under construction.

During the process of improving the banking system, the state bank, while maintaining its central position in the credit system, handed over the functions of granting loans to enterprises and organizations and carrying out settlements with them to specially specialized banks. That is, the function of the bank to carry out emission activities along with lending activities will be put to an end.

The State Bank has become an institution that manages the activities of specialized banks and conducts the same monetary and credit policy for all banks. As a result of the improvement of the banking system, special specialized banks were created: Industrial Construction Bank, Communal Construction and Social Development Bank, Agro-Industrial Bank, Foreign Economic Activity Bank, Savings Bank, and relations between banks and farms became closer. they retained a certain level of managerial role. In the process of improving the banking system, very important results were achieved, but the established banks could not fully express the characteristics of economic relations, therefore further improvement of the banking system became an objective necessity.

To rebuild the economic system, it is necessary to rely primarily on domestic savings. As a commercial bank enters the financial market with a demand for credit resources, it is necessary not only to collect all savings available in the economy to the maximum extent, but also to effectively influence the formation of savings by limiting current consumption. The deposit policy of commercial banks has a great influence on the formation of savings. In addition to high interest rates, depositors need high security and reliability for bank loans. In addition to safety in making deposits, the client can have sufficient information about commercial banking activities, and with this, he can assess the bank's financial condition. Crediting to enterprises, organizations, residents and various entities occupies the main place in the activity of commercial banks. The bank plays the role of a financial intermediary in organizing the lending process. It attracts idle funds and makes them temporarily available to clients on its own behalf. At the expense of bank credit, important sectors of the economy - industry, agriculture, trade, etc. are financed and become the basis for expanding production.

Commercial banks can attract and place each other's funds in the form of deposits, loans, and carry out other mutual operations specified in their charters on the basis of a contract. In case of lack of funds to provide loans to clients and fulfill their obligations, commercial banks can apply to the Central Bank for credit resources. Interest rates for operations of commercial banks are determined independently by them. But these rates should be based on the policy of interest rates determined in the main directions of the state monetary policy. In the period of transition to a market economy, the main financial resources available in the economy in the underdeveloped stages of the stock market are realized by attracting deposits to banks.

Capitalization of assets occurs as a result of investing resources in various investment objects. These are tools that create an opportunity for business entities to earn income. Therefore, investors invest depending on the level of participation of their assets in the process of generating income. Income is not included in the concept of economic entities. Income is a component of any investment, as it is the source of it. Uzbekistan is also interested in attracting foreign funds. Currently, they mainly come in the form of loans from international organizations and governments of other countries. At the same time, the Republic feels the need for investments, because, unlike loans, investments do not create debt, but directly support the expansion and modernization of production, the development of scientific productive forces. In attracting investors, the factors that interest them in the first place are: economic situation, political situation, legal field, geographical location, institutional organizational technical field. An important direction in the use of investment is concrete project and concrete production. This means that their priority in the distribution of investments available to the entire society at a given time has remained out of competition. This results in the fact that projects implemented at the level of certain enterprises, existing areas need to be developed, and as a result, their infrastructures will be expanded, developed and improved, compatibility between production areas will be ensured, and the condition of the labor team will improve. Free economic zones are being created to attract more investments. A free economic zone is a special territory within the country, where all conditions necessary for highly efficient production of export goods and services have been created based on the active attraction of foreign investment. State regulation of investment relations is organized by creating legal conditions, providing guarantees for conducting this activity, insuring the subjects of this activity and realizing social or state interests through

other means. The essence of investment relations is expressed in the scope and level of the participants of this activity.

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